

THE MOST-CITED WORKS IN BRAIN ARTERIOVENOUS MALFORMATIONS: BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF 100 MOST CITED ARTICLES AND TREND IN CITATION CLASSICS

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ABSTRACT

Background The number of times that a published article is cited is one indicator of its scientific impact. There is an abundance of articles published on brain arteriovenous malformation [AVM]. Bibliometric analyses are useful in determining most impactful studies within this field. This study aims to evaluate most cited works in brain AVM using bibliometric analyses to identify most relevant research and newest trends. **Methods:** Brain AVM specific search using Harzing publish or Perish publicly assessable software that indexes citations from Google Scholar were performed in May 2017. Full length articles 100 most cited articles were reviewed base on the aim of this study. **Results:** After a detailed search, 164 articles with a total number of 36776 citations over 68 year period were obtained. Further analysis performed to obtain the 100 most cited works. The top 10 most cited article obtained further. The top 100 papers included were cited on average of 295 times per year ranged 104 to 1827. Publication date ranged from 1981 to 2014. Sixty-six of the 100 articles were from the United States of America, 11 from Canada, over 15 from Europe. The journal publishing the highest number of the top 100 highly cited articles was Journal of Neurosurgery with 38 publications. The most corresponding authors were from neurosurgical speciality. **Conclusion** This current report provides analysis of the most influential works in brain AVM research describing the trend of most cited works with its comprehensive list.

KEYWORDS Brain arteriovenous malformations; bibliometric analysis; citation classics

Introduction

Brain arteriovenous malformations (AVMs) are abnormal connections between arteries and veins leading to arteriovenous shunting with an intervening network of vessels termed nidus [1]. This was first described by Steinheil in 1895, arteriovenous

brain malformations (BAVMs) are a complex of abnormal arteries and veins that directly fistulize without an intervening capillary bed. From a purely categorical level, BAVMs differ from other fistulous vascular malformations, such as a vein of Galen malformations, dural arteriovenous fistulas, or secondary malformations that arise from trauma, or neovascularization that occurs after chronic cerebral venous occlusion [2]. Brain AVM has been recognised as a significant cause of death, long-term morbidity due to intracranial haemorrhage and epilepsy. It is often difficult to quantify the significance of a given published work. However, one useful index of influence is the total number of citations accrue overtime by the published article if more than 400 citations referred to as citation classics[3]. Identifying these highly cited works is essential to clinicians and researcher

Copyright © 2018 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI: 10.5455/IJMRCR.Most-Cited-Works-Brain-Arteriovenous-Malformations
First Received: June 04, 2018
Accepted: July 02, 2018
Reviewers: Slavomir Kondoff (BG); Junfei Zhao (USA)
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Table 1 Top 10 Brain arteriovenous malformation-specific citations classics

Rank	Citation	First Author	Title	year	Journal	Country
1	1827	R.F Speltzler	A proposed grading system for arteriovenous malformations	1986	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
2	1017	S.L Ondra	The natural history of symptomatic arteriovenous malformation of the brain: 24 years follow up assessment	1990	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
3	827	W.F McCormick	The pathology of vascular (arteriovenous) malformation	1966	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
4	758	C.J Graf	Bleeding from cerebral arteriovenous malformation as a part of the natural history	1983	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
5	752	L.D Lunsford	Stereotactic radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformation of the brain	1991	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
6	734	P.M Crawford	Arteriovenous malformation of the brain; natural history in unoperated patients	1986	Journal of Neurology Neurosurgery & Psychiatry	UK
7	634	R.D Brown Jr	The natural history of unruptured intracranial arteriovenous malformations	1988	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
8	606	L. Steiner	Clinical outcome of radiosurgery for cerebral arteriovenous malformation	1992	Journal of Neurosurgery	Sweden
9	578	R.N Kjellberg	Bragg-peak proton-beam therapy for arteriovenous malformation of the brain	1983	New England Journal of Medicine	USA
10	469	C. Stapf	Predictors of haemorrhage in patients with untreated brain arteriovenous malformations	2006	Neurology	USA

for evidence-based practice and current research trend and focus in brain arteriovenous malformation. Also, citation classics represent the highest impact work in a specific field and offer insights to a high area of research within this field.

Group analysis of these articles will serve to understand the changing landscape and trend in this field over time. This can be termed bibliometric analyses, has been previously applied to few subspecialties in neurosurgery such as epilepsy [4], pain [5] and skull base neurosurgery [6]

In spite of the rise in bibliometric analyses, currently, no such analyses have been performed for brain AVMs research. This article aims to present a detailed and extensive bibliometric analysis of the most highly cited works related to brain AVM describing the changing trends and citation classics for investigators in this field.

Methods Search Strategy

To identify highly cited works in brain AVM, we performed a generalised search using Harzing publish or perish [7], free accessible software search engine easily accessible to the public, it indexes raw citations from Google scholar with numerous journal articles and corresponding citation. The search was performed in May 2017 without restriction of publication date. Search term used was “arteriovenous brain malformation”, “cerebral arteriovenous malformation”, “intracranial arteriovenous malformation”. Also, a supplementary search was conducted using most cited authors name derived from previous search terms; authors included were Speltzler RF, SL Ondra, WF McCormick, Graf CJ, Steiner L, Brown RD Jr, Kjellerg RN, Stapf C, Faults D. and many more.

This search was field sensitive [4] rather than field specific, that is to say, articles related to Brain AVM in neurosurgery, neurosciences and other health-related publications. Inclusion criteria were articles relevant to the field of brain AVM and published in peer-reviewed journal. We included clinical articles, systematic reviews, meta-analysis and non-systematic reviews (narrative reviews). The full-length articles with citation of 100 and above in the field of Brain AVM research were obtained and extensively reviewed. Articles related to aneurysmal subarachnoid haemorrhage were excluded. The full-length articles of 100 most cited works were obtained and reviewed.

Data coding and Analysis

After rigorous collection of 100 most cited articles with specific data collected from each article for some citations, publication year, and the name of first author, the title of the article, speciality and country of the corresponding author at the time of publication. The data on most cited articles are ranked in descending order by citation numbers.

Results

After detailed and rigorous analyses of 164 articles with a total number of 36776 citations over a 68-year period were obtained. Further analysis performed to get the 100 most cited works. The top 10 most cited article are presented in Table 1 full list of the 100 most cited articles can be found in Supplementary Table 1.

The top 100 papers included were cited on average of 295 times per year ranged 104 to 1827. Publication date ranged from 1981 to 2014. Speltzler et al. published the most frequently cited article (1827 citations). In 1986 in Journal of Neurosurgery titled “A proposed grading system for arteriovenous malformation”.

Table 2 Countries of origin of top-cited articles

Country	Number of Articles
United States of America	66
Canada	11
United Kingdom	3
Sweden	3
Australia	3
Japan	3
Germany	2
Italy	2
Finland	1
Norway	1
Netherlands	1
Switzerland	1
France	1
Greece	1
Turkey	1

Sixty-six of the 100 articles were from the United States of America, 11 from Canada, over 15 from Europe (Table 2). The journal publishing the highest number of the top 100 highly cited articles was Journal of Neurosurgery with 38 publications. Journal publishing two or more than highly cited works are presented in Table 3. Christian Stapf and Bruce Pollock were the most prolific primary authors in the top 100 cited articles with four papers each [Table 4]. The most corresponding authors were from neurosurgical speciality.

The citation classics (article cited more than 400 times) were published in seven different journals (Supplementary data) with 13 identified citation classics. The journal that published the greatest number of citation classics was a journal of Neurosurgery with seven papers

Table 3 Journal (with more than two articles) in most cited articles in brain arteriovenous malformation.

Journal	Number of Articles
Journal of Neurosurgery	38
Neurosurgery	18
Stroke	13
Lancet	5
America Journal of Neuroradiology	4
New England Journal of Medicine	3
Neurology	2
Journal of America Medical Association	2

Table 4 The most common primary authors with more than one articles of the top 100 cited articles in brain arteriovenous malformation.

First Author	Number of Article	Current Affiliation
Christian Stapf	4	Stroke and Neurological Institute, Columbia University, New York, USA
Bruce E Pollock	4	Neurosurgery, Mayo Clinic, USA
William A Friedman	3	Neurosurgery, University of Florida USA
Michael T Lawton	3	Neurological Surgery, University of California San Francisco, USA
Robert F Spetzler	2	Barrows Neurological Institute, Phoenix, Arizona, USA
Robert A Willinsky	2	Interventional Neuroradiology, University of Toronto, Canada
Michael K Morgan	2	Neurosurgery, Macquarie University, Sidney Australia
GM Debrum	2	Neurosurgery, University of Illinois, Chicago, USA
Alfred J Luessenhop	2	Neurosurgery Georgetown University, Washington DC [Retired 1993]
A.Hartmann	2	
J H Choi	2	

Figure 1: Publication trend over the years

Discussion:

In this study, we identified 100 most cited articles in the field of brain AVM research. Bibliometric analyses do not necessarily provide an evaluation of the quality of research of its impact on clinical practice, but they portray historical account research publication with its changing landscapes of a scientific question and significant trend of knowledge been accumulated over the time. Trends in highly cited works allow projections and planning future focus of high-impact and landmark research in a particular field.

Highly cited articles are one of the indicators of most influential work in a given field hence its imperative for clinicians and academic community to be familiar with these articles as a template for evidence-based practice and platform for further research. This study identified only one randomised control trial in the top 100 most cited articles and had been termed the first-ever randomised controlled trial of a therapeutic intervention to improve the prognosis of brain arteriovenous malformation (Medical management with or without interventional therapy for unruptured AVM). However, it was stopped early because of problems. This shows that lots of research still needed in brain AVM.

We compared citation classics of this study with other disciplines (Table 5), most massive citation classics was from Parkinson disease however neurological citations from brain AVM has the least number of randomised controlled trial, just 1%, while aneurysmal subarachnoid haemorrhage 7%. The rate of citation varies significantly among disciplines; it may be that in brain AVM research citations are accumulated at a slower pace than other disciplines [7]

Table 5 Comparison between citation classics in B-AVM, aSAH, Epilepsy and Parkinson's disease

Topic	bAVM	aSAH	Epilepsy	Parkinson disease
Year of conducting citations search	2017	2015	2012	2011
Number of citations classics identified	13	73	89	107
Most cited time	1990-1999	1990-1999	1990-1999	1990-1999
Highest citation number of an article	1827	2763	3749	4327
Top journal				
Randomised control trial	1%	7%	7%	5%
Database search	Google scholar	Google scholar	Google scholar	Thomson Reuters web of science

Limitations

There are several limitations of our studies synonymous with most bibliometric studies including the possibility of missing highly cited work as a result of a single database search strategy. Articles absence from the list of most cited works is not an indicator of inferior impact to clinical practice. Citation provides a global indicator of landmark publication in a specific field, and this serves as a significant guide for essential and essential literature for researchers

Rank	Citation	First Author	Title	year	Journal	Country
1	1827	R.F Speltzler	A proposed grading system for arteriovenous malformations	1986	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
2	1017	S.L Ondra	The natural history of symptomatic arteriovenous malformation of the brain: 24 years follow up assessment	1990	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
3	827	W.F McCormick	The pathology of vascular (arteriovenous) malformation	1966	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
4	758	C.J Graf	Bleeding from cerebral arteriovenous malformation as a part of the natural history	1983	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
5	752	L.D Lunsford	Stereotactic radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformation of the brain	1991	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
6	734	P.M Crawford	Arteriovenous malformation of the brain; natural history in unoperated patients	1986	Journal of Neurology Neurosurgery & Psychiatry	UK
7	634	R.D Brown Jr	The natural history of unruptured intracranial arteriovenous malformations	1988	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
8	606	L. Steiner	Clinical outcome of radiosurgery for cerebral arteriovenous malformation	1992	Journal of Neurosurgery	Sweden
9	578	R.N Kjellberg	Bragg-peak proton-beam therapy for arteriovenous malformation of the brain	1983	New England Journal of Medicine	USA
10	469	C. Stapf	Predictors of haemorrhage in patients with untreated brain arteriovenous malformations	2006	Neurology	USA
11	457	C.S Oglivy	Recommendation for the management of intracranial arteriovenous malformation	2001	Stroke	USA
12	444	D.Fults	Natural history of arteriovenous malformation of the brain: a clinical study	1984	Neurosurgery	USA
13	403	A.J Luessenhop	Artificial embolisation of cerebral arteries: report of use in case of arteriovenous malformation	1960	Journal of America Medical Association	USA

14	388	Y. Gobin	Treatment of brain arteriovenous malformation by embolisation and radiosurgery	1996	Journal of Neurology	USA
15	386	M.G Hamilton	The prospective application of the grading system of arteriovenous malformation	1994	Neurosurgery	USA
16	385	R.F Spetzler	Relationship of perfusion pressure and size to the risk of haemorrhage from an arteriovenous malformation	1992	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
17	384	D.M.C Forster	Arteriovenous malformation of the brain: a long-term clinical study	1972	Journal of Neurosurgery	Sweden
18	350	R Jahan	Embolisation of arteriovenous malformation with onyx: clinicopathological experience in 23 patients	2001	Neurosurgery	USA
19	348	G. Redekop	An arterial aneurysm associated with cerebral arteriovenous malformation: classification, incidence and risk of haemorrhage	1998	Journal of Neurosurgery	Canada
20	344	B.E Pollock	Factors associated with successful arteriovenous malformation radiosurgery	1998	Neurosurgery	USA
21	341	W.A Friedman	Linear accelerator radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformation: relationship of size to the outcome	1995	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
22	331	R. Al-Shahi	A systematic review of the frequency and prognosis of arteriovenous malformation in adults	2001	Brain	UK
23	331	H. Nornes	A hemodynamic aspect of cerebral arteriovenous malformation	1980	Journal of Neurosurgery	Norway
24	326	I.G Fleetwood	Arteriovenous malformation	2002	Lancet	USA
25	318	J.P Mohr	Medical management with or without interventional therapy for unruptured arteriovenous malformation [ARUBA]; a multicentre non-blinded RCT	2014	Lancet	USA
26	318	G. K Steinberg	Stereotactic heavy charged particles Bragg-peak radiation for intracranial arteriovenous malformation	1990	New Journal of England	USA

27	310	B.E Pollock	Haemorrhage after stereotactic radiosurgery for cerebral arteriovenous malformation	1996	Neurosurgery	USA
28	303	J.A Hernesniemi	Natural history of brain arteriovenous malformation: a long-term follow-up study of risk of haemorrhage in 238 patients	2008	Neurosurgery	Finland
29	302	F.Vinuela	Combined endovascular embolisation and surgery in the management of arteriovenous malformation: an experience with 101 cases.	1991	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
30	297	C. Hofmeister	Demographic, morphological and clinical characteristics of 1289 patients with brain arteriovenous malformation	2000	Stroke	Germany
31	297	JA Jane	The natural history of an aneurysm and arteriovenous malformation	1985	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
32	297	B.F Scheider	Histopathology of arteriovenous malformation after gamma knife radiosurgery	1997	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
33	287	P.P Han	Intention-to-treat analysis of Spetzler-Martin Grade IV and V arteriovenous malformation: natural history and paradigm	2003	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
34	278	K. Maruyama	Risk of haemorrhage after radiosurgery for cerebral arteriovenous malformation	2005	New England Journal of Medicine	Japan
35	260	A.J Luessenhop	Cerebral arteriovenous malformation: indications for and results of surgery and role of intravascular techniques	1984	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
36	259	G.M Debrum	Embolization of cerebral arteriovenous malformation with bucrylate: experience in 46 cases	1982	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
37	252	W.A Friedman	The risk of haemorrhage after radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformations	1996	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
38	250	J.J Jafar	The effect of embolisation with N-butyl cyanoacrylate before surgical resection of cerebral	1993	Journal of	USA

			arteriovenous malformations		Neurosurgery	
39	250	W.Weber	Endovascular treatment of intracranial arteriovenous malformation with onyx; technical aspects	2007	America Journal of Neuroradiology	Germany
40	249	D. Parkinson	Arteriovenous malformations; summary of 100 consecutive supratentorial cases	1980	Journal of Neurosurgery	Canada
41	248	L. da Costa	Natural history and predictive features of haemorrhage from brain arteriovenous malformation	2009	Stroke	Canada
42	244	J Van Beijnum	Treatment of brain arteriovenous malformation: a systematic review and meta-analysis	2011	Journal of America Medical Association	Netherlands
43	241	B.E Pollock	A proposed radiosurgery grading for arteriovenous malformations	2002	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
44	238	G.M Debrum	Embolization of the nidus of brain arteriovenous malformation with butyl cyanoacrylate	1997	Neurosurgery	USA
45	238	Y. Miyasaka	Analysis of venous drainage system as a factor in haemorrhage from arteriovenous malformations	1992	Journal of Neurosurgery	Japan
46	237	R.M Friedlander	Arteriovenous malformations of the brain	2007	New England Journal of Medicine	USA
47	230	F. Turjman	Correlation of the angioarchitecture of cerebral arteriovenous malformation with the clinical presentation of haemorrhage	1995	Neurosurgery	USA
48	225	D. Fournier	Endovascular treatment of intracranial arteriovenous malformations: experience in 49 cases	1991	Journal of Neurosurgery	Canada
49	222	A. Valavanis	Endovascular treatment of brain arteriovenous malformation	1998	Advanced and Technical standard in Neurosurgery	Switzerland
50	218	Y. Itoyama	The natural course of unoperated intracranial arteriovenous malformations: a study of 50 cases	1989	Journal of Neurosurgery	Japan

51	218	V. Katsaridis	Curative embolisation of cerebral arteriovenous malformations with Onyx in 101 patients	2008	Neuroradiology	Greece
52	215	W.A Friedman	Linear accelerator radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformations	1992	Journal of Neurosurgery	Japan
53	212	C. Mounayer	Nidal embolisation of brain arteriovenous malformation using Onyx in 94 patients	2007	America Journal of Neuroradiology	France
54	207	C.G Drake	Posterior fossa arteriovenous malformations	1986	Journal of Neurosurgery	Canada
55	201	B.E Pollock	Repeat stereotactic radiosurgery of arteriovenous malformations: factors associated with incomplete obliteration	1996	Neurosurgery	USA
56	200	J.H Choi	Brain arteriovenous malformations in adults	2005	Lancet Neurology	USA
57	199	Y. Yamamoto	Interim report of the radiological treatment of cerebral arteriovenous malformation: influence of size, dose and time on technical obliteration rate	1995	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
58	198	L. Miyawaki	Five-year results of LINAC radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformations: outcome of large arteriovenous malformations	1999	International Journal of Radiation Oncology, Biology and Physics	USA
59	198	R.T Frizzel	Cure, morbidity and mortality associated with embolisation of brain arteriovenous malformations: a review of 1246 patients in 32 series over a 35-year period	1995	Neurosurgery	USA
60	189	A.Kader	Recurrent cerebral arteriovenous malformations after a negative postoperative angiogram	1996	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
61	188	J.L Robinson	Arteriovenous malformation aneurysm and pregnancy	1974	Journal of Neurosurgery	UK
62	185	I.Saatci	Endovascular treatment of brain arteriovenous malformations with prolonged intranidal onyx injection technique: long-term	2011	Journal of	Turkey

			results in 350 consecutive patients		Neurosurgery	
63	179	M.T Lawton	Multimodality of deep arteriovenous malformations: thalamus, basal ganglia and brainstem	1995	Neurosurgery	USA
64	179	B. Guidetti	Intracranial arteriovenous malformations; consecutive and surgical treatment	1980	Journal of Neurosurgery	Italy
65	173	H.T ApSimon	A population-based study of brain arteriovenous malformations	2002	Stroke	Australia
66	170	A.Hartmann	Risk of endovascular treatment of arteriovenous brain malformations	2002	Stroke	USA
67	166	D. Kondziolka	Arteriovenous malformation of the brain: A forty year experience	1992	Canadian Journal of Neurosciences	Canada
68	164	M.F Berman	Epidemiology of brain arteriovenous malformation	2000	Neurosurgery	USA
69	164	M. Soderman	Management of patients with brain arteriovenous malformation	2003	European Journal of Radiology	Sweden
70	163	M.T Lawton	A supplementary grading scale for selecting patients with brain arteriovenous malformations for surgery	2010	Neurosurgery	USA
71	161	AX Halim	Longitudinal risk of intracranial haemorrhage in patients with arteriovenous malformations of the brain in a defined population	2004	Stroke	USA
72	158	J.C Flickinger	Radiosurgery and brain tolerance: analysis of neurodiagnostic imaging changes after gamma knife radiosurgery for arteriovenous malformations	1992	International Journal of Radiation Oncology, Biology 7 Physics	USA
73	152	A.Hartmann	The determinant of neurological outcome after surgery for brain arteriovenous malformations	2000	Stroke	USA
74	152	B.M Stein	Arteriovenous malformations of the brain: current concepts and treatment	1980	Archives of Neurology	USA

75	152	J. Maldjian	Functional magnetic resonance imaging of regional brain activities of patients with intracerebral arteriovenous malformations	1996	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
76	150	C.L Taylor	Complications of preoperative embolization of cerebral arteriovenous malformations	2004	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
77	149	B.L Hoh	Results of multimodal treatment of 141 patients with brain arteriovenous malformations and seizures	2002	Neurosurgery	USA
78	148	R.C Lawson	Treatment of arteriovenous malformation of the brain with combined embolization and stereotactic radiosurgery	1990	America Journal of Neuroradiology	USA
79	147	R.A Willinsky	Multiple cerebral arteriovenous malformations	1990	Neuroradiology	Canada
80	145	M.A Stefani	Large and deep arteriovenous malformations are associated with risk of future haemorrhage	2002	Stroke	Canada
81	142	P. Celli	Cerebral arteriovenous malformation in children: clinical features and outcome in children and adults	1984	Surgical Neurology	Italy
82	141	J.A Marthis	The efficacy of particulate embolisation combined with stereotactic radiosurgery for the treatment of large arteriovenous malformations of the brain	1995	America Journal of Neuroradiology	USA
83	140	J.H Choi	Clinical outcome after first and recurrent haemorrhage in patients with untreated brain arteriovenous malformations	2006	Stroke	USA
84	140	M.A Stefani	Angioarchitectural factors present in brain arteriovenous malformations associated with haemorrhage presentation	2002	Stroke	Canada
85	138	M.T Lawton	Effect of presenting haemorrhage on outcome after microsurgical resection of brain arteriovenous malformations	2005	Neurosurgery	USA

86	133	C.J Ledezma	Complications of cerebral arteriovenous malformations: multivariate analysis of predictive factors	2006	Neurosurgery	USA
87	131	M.K Morgan	Complications of surgery for arteriovenous malformations of the brain	1993	Journal of Neurosurgery	Australia
88	130	R.A Willinsky	Brain arteriovenous malformations: analysis of angioarchitecture in relationship to haemorrhage	1987	Journal of Neuroradiology	Canada
89	129	W.F Yakes	Ethanol endovascular management of brain arteriovenous malformations: initial results	1997	Neurosurgery	USA
90	129	S.K Natarajan	Multimodality treatment of brain arteriovenous malformation with microsurgery after embolisation	2008	Neurosurgery	USA
91	127	T. Hashimoto	Abnormal expression of matrix metalloproteinases and tissue inhibitors in metalloproteinases in brain arteriovenous malformations	2003	Stroke	USA
92	121	S. Hayashi	The association of an intracranial aneurysm and arteriovenous malformations of the brain: a case report	1981	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
93	121	C.S Haw	Complications of embolization of arteriovenous malformations of the brain	2006	Journal of Neurosurgery	Canada
94	120	C. Stapf	Invasive treatment of unruptured arteriovenous malformations is an experimental therapy	2006	Current Opinion in Neurosurgery	USA
95	119	H.J Perata	Feeding artery pedicle aneurysm association with parenchyma haemorrhage and arteriovenous malformations in the brain	1994	Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
96	117	C.Stapf	A concurrent arterial aneurysm in brain arteriovenous malformations with haemorrhagic presentations	2002	Neurology	USA
97	116	A.V Khaw	Association of infratentorial brain arteriovenous malformations with haemorrhage at initial presentations	2004	Stroke	USA

98	110	C.Stapf	Effect of age on clinical or morphological characteristics of patients with brain arteriovenous malformations	2003	Stroke	USA
99	107	R.A Solomon	Management of arteriovenous malformations of the brain		Journal of Neurosurgery	USA
100	104	M.K Morgan	The surgical risk associated with management of Grade 1 & II brain arteriovenous malformations	2007	Neurosurgery	Australia

Conclusion

Brain AVM remains an area of tremendous but slow academic interest and neurosurgeons interest in this field has been slow. This is reflected in the trend and quantity of published work. Also, there has been a significant shift in clinical practice towards endovascular treatment due to better and improved technologies.

Authors' Statements

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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